

REOO- AUTOMATED SLIDER CRANK MECHANISM.

STUDENT INDUSTRIAL WORK EXPERIENCE SCHEME I [S.I.W.E.S] REPORT

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BY

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DEDICATION

This report is dedicated foremost to God Almighty for his favour, mercy and grace upon our lives, especially during the 9 weeks SIWES programme at the School of Science and Technology, Pan Atlantic University. We would also like to dedicate it to our parents and siblings for their love and support and to everyone else that contributed to making the SIWES experience a fun and successful one.

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TITLE OF INVENTION:

REOO- Automated Slider Crank Mechanism.

Final Product Preview

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ABSTRACT:

Machines play a very important role in different manufacturing processes in today's industry because they are the foundation of automation. REOO invention relates to an automated slider-crank mechanism, which comprises a motor rotating the crank, and transfers the rotational motion to linear on the slider through the aid of a connecting rod between the crank and the slider. This mechanism is frequently utilized to investigate machine kinematics and resulting dynamic forces. The acceleration, position, velocity and change in displacement of the slider during motion can be determined through analytical modelling of the mechanism. This invention aims to produce an automated slider crank mechanism using locally sourced materials that demonstrates the transfer of rotational motion into linear motion. The production cost of the locally fabricated device is N30,000.00k and the cost of the conventional imported device is \$750.00 (N321,600.00k). Therefore, the locally produced slider-crank mechanism device is far cheaper and can be used as a substitute for the imported equipment in tertiary institutions in Nigeria laboratories. In conclusion, the fabrication of REOO slider-crank mechanism was successful, with minimal variation from the original design required. Specified tolerances of interfacing parts were met and functioned as intended. Assembly was conducted through a procedure that allowed for incremental adjustments, minimizing system friction. All experimental values show similar trend when compared with analytical calculations.

Keywords:

Slider crank mechanism, cost, automation, kinematics, motion.

Technical Field:

- Teaching Aid:

The Slider crank return mechanism is a common mechanism used to investigate the kinematics and dynamics of simple machines. It is used in laboratory courses such as Engineering Mechanics (GET 207). The knowledge of important concepts in courses such as Engineering materials (GET 211) helps in the proper selection of the material needed for fabrication. Computer Aided Engineering (GET 212) aids in engineering simulation and control of the motor required to automate this mechanism.

- Mechanical engineering:

The slider crank mechanism is a fundamental concept of how the combustion engine works, Slider-crank mechanism is used in the piston-cylinder assembly in combustion engines and converts reciprocating motion into circular motion and vice-versa.

- Electrical engineering:

The Control of the mechanism is done through the use of microcontrollers, motors, and interconnected circuits to demonstrate an automated transfer of motion. This has been applied through the knowledge gained from the Fundamentals of Electrical Engineering (GET 202).

Background:

Literature Review:

The classic form of the slider-crank mechanism consists of a piston, cylinder, connecting rod, and crankshaft. In general, the rotational motion of the shaft is converted to a linear displacement of the piston. The slider crank mechanism has been used throughout history, in flour-sifting, treadle spinning wheels, water-powered furnace bellows, and silk-reeling machines by the Western Han Dynasty (202 BC - 9 AD). A ¹device shown in the early 9th-century Carolingian manuscript Utrecht Psalter is a crank handle used with a rotary grindstone.

Scholars point to the use of crank handles in trepanation drills in a 10th-century work by the Spanish Muslim surgeon Abu al-Qasim al-Zahrawi (936–1013). An Arabic inventor, Al-Jazari (1136–1206), described a crank and connecting rod system in a rotating machine in two of his water-raising machines. His twin-cylinder pump incorporated the earliest known crankshaft, while his other machine incorporated the first known crank-slider mechanism. Slider cranks have many applications, the most common of which are engines. The use of these mechanisms for power generation began in the late 18th century with the steam engine and has progressed to the most recognizable form today, the internal combustion engine.

Almost all reciprocating engines use cranks to transform the back-and-forth motion of the pistons into rotary motion. ²The recent application of an automated slider crank mechanism in addition to the cam mechanism is used to make a flexible drive of an automatic bandsaw blade sharpening machine to have to change the drive mechanism when sharpening different bandsaw blades. It is also used in the ³Hybrid Offset Slider Crank Mechanism for Anthropomorphic Flexion in Prosthetic Hands to address the challenge of emulating the

anthropomorphic flexion movement by using a hybrid mechanism using both linkage-based offset slider-crank-based finger designed using a combination of different diameters of cranks and different length of connecting rods and tendon-driven actuation.

There has been a common ⁴trend of imperfection in most of the existing works in machining the parts. It is vital to compensate for potential errors in the machine and verify that the final size would meet the requirements dictated by these fits. The variation from the desired size has to be accounted for and the appropriate offsets adjusted to generate the desired dimension. This error comes as a result of several factors including, variation in probe calibration, and accuracy, tool wear, tool deflection, and overall machine capability.

Research Problem Statement:

Nigeria is well known for excessive reliance on the importation of most equipment used in our everyday life. Research through questionnaires has shown that most Universities and industries rely on imported machines, and this has been a drawback to the technological advancement of the country. Simple mechanics such as the Slider Crank Mechanism a very important tool in the demonstration of machine kinematics in learning institutions. The importation of this mechanism has a high comparative loss than when it is being fabricated in the home country.

T-test research done by ⁵Prof Sangotayo, the T-test shows that the constructed apparatus and standard imported slider-crank mechanism apparatus experiment have the t-Stat value, lesser than the critical value (1.690923455) for one tail and 2.032243174 for two tail

examination. Hence there is no significant difference between the two devices' results at 95% confidence. Therefore, the locally produced slider-crank mechanism device is cheaper and can be used as a substitute for the imported equipment in tertiary institutions in Nigeria laboratories. The slider-crank mechanism apparatus in the laboratory is imported, with a high cost and lengthy delivery time, thereby making it difficult to acquire more than one device for a broad set of students offering Mechanics of Machines and other related courses.

Due to limited time and monetary resources, engineers need to look inward for the locally produced slider-crank mechanism apparatus with the local content of the production. It has been reported, that for technological advancement to flourish in Nigeria, enhancement, and manufacture of the most needed equipment and machines must be based on native designs (Charles-Owaba, 2009, Ismaila, 2008, Akintayo,2009). These will ensure the conservation of foreign exchange earnings, maintainability, and affordability to average Nigerian Institutions.

Summary of the Invention

The REOO slider crank is a simple slider crank mechanism which is automated. The mechanism is automated using a DC motor powered by a battery or rectified AC adaptor. The motor is situated below the crank and rotates it, which in turn moves the connecting rod causing the slider to make linear oscillating motions. The speed at which the motor rotates is regulated by a constructed Arduino speed controller. This, therefore, regulates the speed of the crank and slider.

Since there is a lot of contact between the moving parts in the mechanism, there are limitations such as: wearing and tearing of the material at joints, hindrance of movement between parts such as in the slider and loss of mechanical and electrical energy in the crank due to the frictional forces present between the parts. The invention could assist the learning of young engineers by giving them an understanding of the operation of the mechanism behind so many mechanical machines such as car engines and pumps.

Aims and Objectives:

Aims

- To fabricate an Automated slider crank mechanism using materials available in the country.

Objectives:

- Mathematical modelling of a highly efficient slider crank mechanism.
- 3D Modelling design of the slider crank mechanism using Fusion 360.
- Fabrication and construction of parts to fit.
- Automation of fabricated Slider crank mechanism.

Applications of the slider crank mechanism:

The slider crank mechanism finds extensive use in reciprocating compressors, piston engines, presses, toggle devices, and other machines where force characteristics are essential. The slider crank mechanism is such a versatile mechanism for different applications. It can be found in household electronics like an electric toothbrush, the compressor of the refrigerator, etc.

In outdoor considerations; the slider-crank mechanism can be found in lawnmowers, cars, trucks, etc. In industrial applications, the slider-crank mechanism can be found in industrial compressors, boilers, turbines, turbochargers, etc. Just put the use of slider-crank mechanism cuts across every sphere and level of human existence ⁵.

Industrial machines that use the Slider Crank mechanism:

- Reciprocating engine.
- Rotary engine.
- Winch.
- Hand Pump.
- Sun and planet gear.
- Nothing grinder.

Manufacturing and Conceptual Drawings:

Design Aim

Using Fusion 360, a 3 dimensional model of the proposed Slider Crank was assembled. It comprised of six components:

- Crank.
- Connecting Rod.
- Slider.
- C section
- Grounded base
- Fittings

List of Figures:

1. Crank:

Figure 1: Crank

Manufacturing Drawing

2. Connecting Rod:

Figure 2: Connecting Rod

Manufacturing Drawing

3. Slider:

Figure 3: Sliding Block

Manufacturing Drawing

4. C-SECTION:

Figure 4: C Section

Manufacturing Drawing

5. Screws:

Figure 5: Screws

Manufacturing Drawing

6. Ground base:

Figure 6 Base

Manufacturing Drawing

Assembled Drawing:

Assembled view

Manufacturing Drawing

Invention Description:

The REOO slider-crank mechanism is an automated return mechanism that exhibits both linear and rotational motion simultaneously. This mechanism can be broken down into two systems, the mechanical system and the electrical system.

The mechanical system refers to the components required for the kinematics of the mechanism; it can be broken into three main components they are:

1. Slider

2. Connecting rod.

3. Crank.

- The Slider is the straight component that is transformed into linear motion. It is guided at both sides with a base to ensure total transformation of the rotatory motion from the crank to linear on the slider.
- The Connecting rod is the joining component that connects the slider and the crank, it is usually expected to be the longest component as a result of the distance between the crank and the slider.
- The Crank is the circular and driving component of the REOO mechanism, it provides the rotational motion that is needed to be transformed to linear on the Slider.

The electrical system refers to the components needed to automate this mechanism. It involves the use of concepts learnt in both the Fundamental of Electrical Engineering (GET 202) and Computer-Aided Engineering (GET 212). It comprises components such as an Arduino microcontroller, Ultrasonic sensor Module, Dc motor, breadboard, diode and MOSFET.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Preliminary Design Considerations:

The following factors were considered in the construction of the machine would be carried out; Portability, Cost of production, Availability of materials, Reliability, Durability, Ease of operation, Anthropometry and Ergonomics.

Materials Selection:

Most of the material to be used would be sourced within the locality, Lagos to be precise to ensure the reduction of the overall cost of production, thereby achieving one of the cardinal objectives of this project.

Mechanical materials:

1. Mild Steel: Mild steel is a very ready and familiar material in our local environment. It is relatively cheap and easily affordable when compared with cast iron. Mild steel was used for the base of the apparatus because of its high strength, hardness, malleability, machinability, and toughness.
2. Perspex board: This is a transparent material made up of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), it is commonly referred to as acrylic sheet.
3. Aluminium: Aluminium is a light metal which finds application in engine systems where light weight is needed. The crank, connecting rod, and slider were all made from aluminium. Aluminium is preferred because of its lightweight, availability and also because it is cheap and readily available in the local market. The parts stated here would experience relative motion one against another; this brings another characteristic of aluminium to the fore, that is its resistance to wear and tear thereby reducing the need for lubrication.

Based on the application of Engineering Mechanics and Engineering materials. Important concepts in Engineering Materials (GET 211) such as the mechanical properties of materials enable us to consider aluminium as the best material needed to fabricate the slider crank mechanism. The reason for this is because of its lightweight, anti-corrosive property. In Strength of materials (GET 208), for there to be maximum efficiency in the slider, the weight has to be counterbalanced at the crank. The crank should be made as easier to spin as possible to reduce any possible stress and fatigue on the motor.

Due to moving parts across different sides of the mechanism, important concepts such as friction in Engineering Mechanics (GET 207) was studied, for example in the sliding part, the slider has to be aligned along the c-section, and the sides of the slider have to be lubricated to reduce contact friction between two surfaces.

Electronic materials:

1. Arduino Microcontroller:

Front view of an Arduino Microcontroller.

This is essentially the brain of automation. It allows for the implementation of C-codes in order to control the mechanism.

2. Ultrasonic Sensor Module:

An Ultrasonic Sensor measuring distance

This is the sensor that measures the change in displacement of the slider when in motion.

3. Dc motor:

Side view of a DC motor

This is a machine that produces the driving force for the crank to rotate.

Top view of jumper cables

4. Jumper cables: These are thin dc wires that interconnect every electrical component.

5. Breadboard:

Layout of pinholes on a breadboard

This is a layout of pin holes in order to hold each component during circuit construction.

6. Power diode:

Front view of a Power diode

This serves as a protective device connected across the motor.

7. N-channel MOSFET:

Front view of an N-channel MOSFET

This is a type of transistor that helps to amplify the starting current needed to drive the motor.

Opportunity Cost and risk analysis:

The financial overhead of this project costs N30,000.00k. It is evident that the locally fabricated apparatus, cost much less than the imported ones because a Scotch Yoke Mechanism working Model Kit, Engineering Mechanism – a classroom teaching aid for modelling - mini mechanical project - engineering lab equipment cost 1800 pound sterling and others \$750.

MATERIAL	COST
Tap, Dice, washer	₦ 1,750.00
Spray paint (aluminium finish)	₦ 550.00
Screws	₦ 1070.00
Automation	₦ 13,500.00
Stand	₦ 2,600.00
Engraving	₦ 4,000.00
Transportation	₦ 6,530.00
Total	₦ 30,000.00

MODELLING EQUATIONS:

- Slider Crank modelling:

Displacement:

$$x = (r + l) - l \cos \alpha + r \sin \theta$$

$$(r \sin \theta)^2 + (l \cos \alpha)^2 = l^2$$

$$(r^2 \sin^2 \theta) + (l^2 \cos^2 \alpha) = l^2$$

$$(r^2 \sin^2 \theta)^2 = l^2 - (l^2 \cos^2 \alpha)$$

$$(r^2 \sin^2 \theta)^2 = l^2 (1 - \cos^2 \alpha)$$

$$\frac{(r^2 \sin^2 \theta)^2}{l^2} = (1 - \cos^2 \alpha)$$

$$\cos^2 \alpha = 1 - \frac{(r^2 \sin^2 \theta)^2}{l^2}$$

$$\cos \alpha = \sqrt{1 - \frac{(r^2 \sin^2 \theta)^2}{l^2}}$$

Substituting,

$$x = (r + l) - (l \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{(r^2 \cdot \sin^2 \theta)}{l^2}} + r \sin \theta)$$

If r/l is small,

$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{(r^2 \cdot \sin^2 \theta)}{l^2}} \cong \left(1 - \frac{(r^2 \cdot \sin^2 \theta)}{l^2}\right)$$

Therefore;

$$x = r \cdot \left(1 - \cos \theta + \frac{r \cdot \sin^2 \theta}{l}\right)$$

NB:

The expressions for velocity and acceleration are derived by successive differentiations

Theta is a function of time therefore for reference:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= r \cdot \sin \theta \\ \frac{dx}{dt} &= r \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt} \cdot \cos \theta \end{aligned}$$

In essence,

Velocity:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = r \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\sin \theta + \frac{r \cdot \sin 2\theta}{2l}\right)$$

$$\text{Acceleration: } \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = r \cdot \omega^2 \cdot \left(\cos \theta + \frac{r \cdot \cos 2\theta}{l}\right)$$

NB:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \omega$$

Torque equation modelling:

Source: MathWorks Images.

The torque required to drive the mechanism can be calculated using the resultant force of the resolution of forces above;

Recall: power= Force x Velocity;

Force=mass x acceleration.

Thus: Power = mass x acceleration x velocity

Recall: Power=torque x angular speed;

Thus torque =power/angular speed

Tables:

Crank angle θ	Experimental displacement (mm)	Theoretical displacement (mm)	Crank angle θ	Experimental displacement (mm)	Theoretical displacement (mm)
10.0	56.1	56.5	190.0	31.0	32.5
20.0	20.3	21.5	200.0	17.7	18.8
30.0	28.3	29.8	210.0	57.2	57.5
40.0	51.7	52.5	220.0	0.1	0.2
50.0	1.3	1.4	230.0	54.8	55.3
60.0	58.9	59.0	240.0	22.9	24.2
70.0	12.8	13.7	250.0	25.6	27.0
80.0	36.3	37.8	260.0	53.3	54.0
90.0	45.8	47.0	270.0	0.6	0.6
100.0	4.9	5.3	280.0	58.1	58.3
110.0	60.0	60.0	290.0	15.2	16.2
120.0	6.6	7.1	300.0	33.7	35.2
130.0	43.6	44.9	310.0	47.9	49.0
140.0	38.8	40.3	320.0	3.4	3.7
150.0	10.6	11.3	330.0	59.8	59.8
160.0	59.4	59.5	340.0	8.5	9.1
170.0	2.2	2.4	350.0	41.3	42.6
180.0	49.9	50.8	360.0	41.3	42.6

Crank angle θ	Experimental Velocity (m/s)	Theoretical Velocity (m/s)	Crank angle θ	Experimental velocity (m/s)	Theoretical velocity (m/s)
10.0	-67.9	-61.1	190.0	151.7	152.6
20.0	148.1	153.7	200.0	-143.8	-150.1
30.0	-152.8	-155.1	210.0	57.8	51.6
40.0	96.9	89.4	220.0	15.9	17.2
50.0	-47.0	-50.7	230.0	-77.9	-70.6
60.0	-37.0	-32.7	240.0	151.1	155.7
70.0	130.8	138.1	250.0	-152.6	-156.1
80.0	-145.8	-144.1	260.0	87.5	80.0
90.0	122.1	116.1	270.0	-31.6	-34.2
100.0	-89.1	-95.6	280.0	-47.4	-42.1
110.0	-5.3	-4.6	290.0	138.0	145.0
120.0	101.3	108.4	300.0	-149.3	-149.0
130.0	-129.3	-124.1	310.0	114.2	107.5
140.0	141.2	138.3	320.0	-75.8	-81.6
150.0	-122.2	-129.7	330.0	-15.9	-14.0
160.0	26.5	23.3	340.0	112.4	119.8
170.0	61.8	66.6	350.0	-135.7	-131.6
180.0	-105.8	-98.6	360.0	135.7	131.6

Crank angle θ	Experimental Acceleration (m/s ²)	Theoretical Acceleration (m/s ²)	Crank angle θ	Experimental Acceleration (m/s ²)	Theoretical Acceleration (m/s ²)
10.0	-598.7	-61.1	190.0	151.7	152.6
20.0	256.0	153.7	200.0	-143.8	18.8
30.0	44.3	-155.1	210.0	57.8	57.5
40.0	-508.5	89.4	220.0	15.9	0.2
50.0	788.4	-50.7	230.0	-77.9	55.3
60.0	-653.2	-32.7	240.0	151.1	24.2
70.0	460.2	138.1	250.0	-152.6	27.0
80.0	-156.0	-144.1	260.0	87.5	54.0
90.0	-380.9	116.1	270.0	-31.6	0.6
100.0	683.3	-95.6	280.0	-47.4	58.3
110.0	-674.6	-4.6	290.0	138.0	16.2
120.0	635.1	108.4	300.0	-149.3	35.2
130.0	-330.2	-124.1	310.0	114.2	49.0
140.0	-217.5	138.3	320.0	-75.8	3.7
150.0	522.8	-129.7	330.0	-15.9	59.8
160.0	-663.9	23.3	340.0	112.4	9.1
170.0	760.5	66.6	350.0	-135.7	42.6
180.0	-470.1	-98.6	360.0	135.7	42.6

GRAPHS ON DISPLACEMENT, VELOCITY AND ACCELERATION

Static Stress Simulation:

Static Stress Simulation using fusion 360

Arduino Programming

```
SPEED_CONTROL | Arduino 1.8.18
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

SPEED_CONTROL $

int PWMPin = 10;
int motorSpeed = 0;
void setup()
{
}
void loop()
{
  for (motorSpeed = 0 ; motorSpeed <=255; motorSpeed += 10)
  {
    analogWrite(PWMPin, motorSpeed);
  }
}
```

Done uploading.

Sketch uses 948 bytes (2%) of program storage space. Maximum is 32256 bytes.
Global variables use 11 bytes (0%) of dynamic memory, leaving 2037 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 2048 bytes.

Arduino Program to Control the speed of the DC Motor.

1. This code is designed to control the speed of the motor using the circuit layout constructed below:

Speed Control Circuit

2. Functional programming:

In order to calculate different experimental values such as slide acceleration, velocity, and displacement. These different functions have been implemented using the Arduino integrated development environment as shown below.


```
SLIDER_CRANK_PROGRAMMING | Arduino 1.8.18
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

SLIDER_CRANK_PROGRAMMING

float DISPLACEMENT_FUNCTION (float r, float w, float l, double t)
{
  float x;
  x= r*(1-cos(t) +z/2*l*(sin(t)*sin(t)));
  return x;
}

//CHANGE IN DISPLACEMENT OF SLIDING BLOCK

float VELOCITY_FUNCTION (float r, float w, float l, double t)
{
  float VELOCITY;
  VELOCITY= r*w*(sin(t) +z/2*l*sin(2*t));
  return VELOCITY ;
}

float ACCELERATION_FUNCTION (float r, float w, float l, double t)
{
  float ACCELERATION;
  VELOCITY= r*w*w*(cos(t) +z/l*cos(2*t));
  return VELOCITY ;
}

Done compiling

Sketch uses 1644 bytes (5%) of program storage space. Maximum is 32256 bytes.
Global variables use 192 bytes (9%) of dynamic memory, leaving 1856 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 2048 bytes.
```

Arduino Program to Calculate the velocity, acceleration and change in displace of Sliding block.

Project management:

CLAIMS:

The REOO slider crank is the first automated return mechanism in Nigeria that encompasses:

1. A simple slider crank mechanism made up of a rotating crank, an oscillating slider and a connecting rod which joins the slider and crank and allows for freedom.
2. A DC motor below the crank which powers the rotation of the crank and automates the mechanism.
3. An Arduino Uno microcontroller board which regulates the electric power and acts as a speed controller.

Conclusion & Recommendation:

Conclusion:

The Fabrication of REOO slider-crank mechanism was successful, with minimal variation from the original design required. Specified tolerances of interfacing parts were met and functioned as intended. Assembly was conducted through a procedure that allowed for incremental adjustments, minimizing system friction. All experimental values were reasonable when compared with analytical calculations. The economic feasibility of the fabricated apparatus with available indigenous materials is better compared to the exorbitant cost of the conventional device which many Nigerian institutions cannot afford. The fabricated device with native elements is affordable to an average Nigerian institution at a production cost of N30,000.00k, as against the sum of \$750.00 (N321,600.00k) for the purchase of the conventional imported device.

Recommendation:

The group considered doing many additional things to the project but due to a combination of time and budgetary constraints not all of these tasks could be completed. Therefore, a number of additional things that could be incorporated into the project which could encompass an entire new REOO slider crank mechanism. Some important things to add to the slider-crank device are highlighted below:

- Motion:

In order to reduce friction due to the sliding part of the mechanism, rollers should be attached at both ends of the slider in order to concentrate movement across a single point of rotation on the roller.

- Automation:

The use of motion and IR sensors alongside the ultrasonic sensor would really help in recording the values of the change in displacement of the Slider.

- Accuracy:

All instruments have finite precision that limits the ability to resolve small measurement differences. One of the best ways to obtain more precise measurements is to use a null difference method instead of measuring a quantity directly. Null or balance methods involve using instrumentation to measure the difference between two similar quantities, one of which is known very accurately and is adjustable.

Contributors:

Oyefusi Samuel (Chief executive officer):

Samuel is a prospective Robotics Engineer responsible for the overall success of a business entity or other organization and for making top-level managerial decisions. He possesses skills such as design, communication, ability to work in teams, pitching skills and other essential entrepreneurial skills, and the ability to organize ideas of every team member in making final decisions. He has worked at several firms as a volunteer in many social functions.

Raehan Kareem (Head of Project Management):

Raehan is an aspiring Electrical Engineer going into his third year. He has a passion for automation and circuitry with the hope that he can apply what he has learnt to produce smarter and more efficient appliances for worldwide use.

Ehirotame Uddin (Production manager & group photographer):

Ehirotame is an electrical and electronics student concerned with the study, design and application of equipment, devices, and systems which use electricity, electronics and electromagnetism.

Caleb Okoro (Document Control manager):

Caleb is a prospective mechanical engineer. He aspires to own his own engineering company where he will be involved in renewable energy and the protection of the environment. Caleb possesses communication skills, entrepreneurship skills, leadership, and design and is still learning more to achieve his goals.

Engr. Paul Onoriode Avbenake (Mentor):

Engr. Paul Onoriode Avbenake is a faculty member at The School of Science and Technology, Pan-Atlantic University. He obtained his B.Sc. in Chemical Engineering from The University of Lagos and M.S.C in the same field from Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. His research interests are Catalysis, Energy, Waste management, Mathematical simulation, and Water harvesting. He has published several journal articles and contributed various book chapters with international publishers as well as presented his research at several international conferences. He is equally a registered COREN, NSChE, and a member of the African Membrane Society (AMS).

Contributions:

Samuel designed the computer-aided design for the slider crank and he procured the components and materials needed for the automated slider crank, Raehan sketched the motion of the slider crank which was shown in the first presentation, Caleb wrote the weekly report from week 1 to week 9 which was submitted to our mentor. Ehirotame and Samuel made the google site, they both ensured to take pictures of the fabrication process and uploaded the deliverables asked of us.

Contributions during the fabrication process:

After the materials were shared among four groups the crank was fabricated by Samuel under the supervision of Engineer Segun, the connecting rod was cut using an angle grinder, milled by all members of the group, the connecting rod was drilled and filled by Ehirotame, the C section (slider frame) was cut and filled by Caleb, all other needed materials frame was gotten by Samuel. An angle grinder was used to remove rust on the frame of the automatic slider crank by Raehan and Ehirotame, its surface was made smooth by Ehirotame using sandpaper, and the acrylic was cut by Raehan and samuel. It was also filled by Caleb, the acrylic was drilled by Raehan, the frame was welded together by group members the frame was painted with anti-rust to prevent rusting by Samuel, Raehan and Ehirotame. It was then spray painted by Raehan, Ehirotame and Samuel by taking turns on each side. The automated slider crank was assembled together and we all constructed a speed controller using Arduino to control the motor.

APPRECIATION:

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